

1. Introduction

Thanks for taking the time to meet with me today.

We are doing a study on the contributors of inner source projects. During the interview, I'd like to ask you a few questions about your background, then we will discuss your experience of inner source projects.

Do you mind if I record this discussion so that I can review it later? In any data collected, or in reports or papers that are published, you will not be identified by name. Please be careful not to discuss any sensitive information about the company you work for. If you do mention any, we will do our best to remove it from our transcripts, but better if you don't mention such sensitive information at all.

2. Demographics

2.1 Years of Experience

How many years of experience do you have in total with software development? And how many years with development of inner source projects?

	Total	Inner Source
Experience (in years)		

2.2 Length of time with [Company/Organization]

Tenure (in years): _____

2.3 Programming Languages

What programming languages do you use in your work?

All	Most frequently used

2.4 Job Responsibility

Next, I'm going to name a series of job responsibilities, and I'd like to tell me where you have "none", "some" or "extensive" experience you have for development with ML and traditional software development.

	Level of Experience (None/Some/Extensive)
Programming	
Design	
Management	
Testing	

2.5 Open source experience

1) Do you have any experience in open source projects? [Yes/No]

- Which project do you mainly contribute to? _____
- How long have been working on this project? _____

2) How much time per week do you spend contributing to open source projects?

- Less than 5 hours/week
- From 5 to 10 hours/week
- From 10 to 20 hours/week
- More than 20 hours/week

3. Inner source experience

1) In your opinion, what is a successful inner source project?

2) How many inner source projects do you participate in? What roles do you play in the projects?

3) Which project do you mainly contribute to? Please kindly describe it in detail.

4) How long have you been working on this project? _____

5) How much time per week do you spend contributing to inner source projects?

- Less than 5 hours/week
- From 5 to 10 hours/week
- From 10 to 20 hours/week
- More than 20 hours/week

4. Motivations

1) What are your main motivations that motivate you start contributing to inner source projects?

2) What are the main reasons for which you are retained in inner source projects?